

THE USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PRESCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM

Azizova Ziroatxon Baxodirovna

Teacher of the Kokand State Pedagogical institute

Kenjaboyeva Sayyora

Student of the Kokand State Pedagogical institute

Abdunazarova Muxsina

Student of the Kokand State Pedagogical institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10217932>

Annotation. The pedagogical process aimed at ensuring the comprehensive development of children in preschool educational organizations is complex, but at the same time colorful. In achieving educational effectiveness, it is necessary to properly organize each type of activity in preschool educational organizations. This article describes the use of modern technologies in preschool educational organizations, and their effectiveness.

Keywords: Education Education, modern technologies, innovation, distance learning.

The economic power of each country, the rise in the level of socio-spiritual life is determined by the competitiveness of the educational system, the progress of science. Therefore, in the strategy of Action for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the priority tasks were set to radically improve the educational sphere, improve the quality of Education, form a generation of intellectual potential, physical perfection, deepen the exact sciences and train qualified personnel for various sectors of the economy, which ultimately provided for the creation of an educational system As a result of reforms in the field, the mechanism of Management in the preschool education system was radically improved, the system of providing non-governmental educational services was reformed, the system of secondary special, vocational education was revised, measures to improve the quality of training of higher education specialists were strengthened, a two-tier system of post-secondary education was introduced. To prepare young people who can live in a rapidly changing world, the traditional educational path, which considers its main task to be to give a certain amount of knowledge, is completely insufficient. Because science and technology have evolved to such an extent that now a person cannot keep even the most basic concepts in a science in his memory. On top of that, young people who are taking an independent step towards a life that has become one of relentless changes may not find their place in a world that consists of a struggle of rivalries if they are not prepared for such changes both

intellectually and spiritually. Currently, rich experiences have been accumulated in the educational system. Chumonchi, business Games, computer training, individualized training, humanism, cooperation, free education of the individual, etc.

Today, the tasks of obtaining templates from foreign experience, implementation in practice with a creative approach, development of regulatory documents, educational and methodological literature, educational methodological complexes in accordance with the requirements of the time, formation of knowledge and skills related to the field of modern management and pedagogical technologies in leaders and specialists of preschool educational organizations on the basis of advanced foreign experience are included in

Preschool education is a major offshoot of continuing education. Previously, this system served only to create a prerequisite for the social activities of fathers who were cocktails in various areas of the national economy, but now the requirements for the content of work in kindergartens have been changed. One of the main tasks is to prepare the little ones to study at the school stage. The development, testing and introduction of new 12-way programs, which are closely modeled after schools' curricula, was initiated in the education of kindergarten educators. In kindergartens, positive results were obtained through the use of these programs in the educational process.

Preschool education specialists agree on the idea that the creation and introduction of innovative ideas in the educational system is a prerequisite for the development of modern kindergarten. The inclusion of state institutions in the daily routine of innovative organizational solutions "when money goes to a preschool teacher" in order of funding significantly increases the prestige of the Institute and determines further development directions. The introduction of innovative technologies in the educational process, taking into account the characteristics of psychophysical age, is always positively felt by preschoolers, who easily change activities. In turn, the initiative pedagogical composition is important, as well as the need to improve the mechanisms of interaction of the parent community, kindergarten with the families of students. Experts say that innovative technologies in the states are not only possible, but also necessary. However, it should be borne in mind that pedagogical technologies, which can be applied in the educational process of pre-existing children, have been given several strict requirements. These include:

- Conceptuality means that the learning process must be based on a certain scientific concept.

- System-related technologies, these technologies must have all the signs inherent in the system. That is, they should be holistic, logical and components of their elements - interrelated.

- Processing-the pedagogical team needs to understand the possibility of setting specific goals, planning the educational process, correcting one or another moment in the work process.

- Reproducibility is the requirement that technology be equally effective regardless of the individual teacher applied to the requirement.

Preschool age is the period when a child actively learns the world around him. Preschool children have their own psychological development characteristics. When you start walking, the child makes a lot of discoveries, gets acquainted with what is located in the room, on the street, in the kindergarten. Collecting various objects, studying them, listening to sounds from the subject, knows what qualities and properties this object has. During this period, the child's visual perception is reduced to - figurative and visual. Effective forms of thinking are created. At the age of 5-6 years, the child, like a sponge, asked for all the information. Scientists have proven that at this young age the child remembers this information, after which he will never remember in life. A child is a period of interest in anything that can expand his horizons, and this will support the world around him.

In general, preschoolers are characterized by a sense of calm. They have no conflicts and strong affective epizootics for minor reasons. However, this does not mean that the saturation of the emotional life of the child decreases. After all, the day of the preschooler is filled with a lot of emotions, so in the evening the child comes to get tired and completely tired. The structure of emotional processes also changes during this period. Previously, motor and vegetative reactions were included in the emotional processes preserved in preschool children, but the external expression of emotions takes on a more limited form.

To date, more than a hundred educational technologies are used in kindergartens in our vast Homeland. Among them, special attention should be paid to:

- health technologies;
- * technologies related to project activities;
- * technologies used in project activities;
- * ICT;
- individual-oriented technologies (person-oriented);
- called Game technologies.

Schoolchildren are upset and happy not only about what they are doing today, but also about what they will do in the future. Everything that belongs to preschool - painting, play, drawing up a mold, helping a mother, doing household chores - should have a bright emotional color, otherwise things will quickly fall off or not at all. Because a child at this age cannot do something that is not interesting to him. In this century, the attitude of preschoolers towards others and themselves is an important indicator. Preschool children often criticize their shortcomings, give personal characteristics to their peers, note the relationship between children and adults, as well as the relationship between adults and adults. However, parents are examples of children. Therefore, parents should not bring fear, anxiety and insult to the child, whether it is personal or intellectual information, to include positive information in the child when the child reaches the age of 6-7 years, he will remember himself in the past in order to realize himself in the present in order to manifest himself in the future.

In this respect, too, this stage accounts for almost 70% of the child's life. That is, in this age range, the child receives more than half of his life's information from the world around him. As the Japanese quotes say, at this age a child should be treated as a king. Because this stage will be rich in important events for child psychology. Preschool education is the primary part of continuing education. He keeps the child formed as a healthy and developed personality and prepares him for systematic teaching, instilling his passion for reading. Preschool education under the age of 6-7 is carried out in state and non-state children's preschool institutions and in the family.

The purpose of preschool education is to prepare children for school education, to form a child as a healthy, developed, independent person, to reveal their abilities, to educate their passion for reading, systematic education. The protection of the life and health of children in a preschool educational institution is carried out by pre-school and state medical personnel, as well as medical personnel of health authorities attached to a preschool educational institution.

The procedure and rules for organizing the protection of the life and health of children in a preschool educational institution, the rules for bringing and taking children to a preschool educational institution, requirements for the organization of safety in the premises of a preschool educational institution, requirements for the organization of fire safety in a preschool educational institution, requirements for the safety of

Preschools are a type of educational institution in the Republic of Uzbekistan and carry out general educational programs during the pre-school

period in different directions. Preschools provide education, training, supervision, care, and wellness for children between the ages of 2 and 7. The order of work of the preschool educational institution and the duration of the stay of children there is determined by the requirements of the state for the quality and level of preschool education, the charter, the contract concluded between the preschool educational institution and parents, as well as by the founders.

Innovative educational technology is a methodology for organizing educational and educational activities, which involves new or qualitative improvement of existing methods and tools to improve the effectiveness of the educational process and create the best conditions for educational and educational activities. current trends in the socio-economic development of society. Innovations in education include complex activities aimed at the emergence of innovations in the field of Education. These innovations can be methods and methods of organizing the educational process, resources used in the educational and educational process, scientific theories and concepts. Innovation develops through the use of research activities aimed at obtaining new scientific knowledge, some kind of discoveries, inventions. In addition, the emergence of innovations can be the result of design work, in which instrumental and technological knowledge develops, reflecting the possibility of carrying out practical actions on the basis of existing scientific theories and concepts. Thus, innovative projects are created, which subsequently lead to the emergence of new technologies. Innovations also develop in the process of educational activities.

In the educational process, theoretical and practical knowledge of students develops, which can then be applied in various areas of practical life related to the creation of innovations. Innovative educational technologies are based on three main components:

Modern, well-structured content, the basis of which is competence in professional activities that meets the current realities of entrepreneurial activity. The content includes various multimedia materials that are transmitted through modern means of communication. Application of modern, innovative teaching methods. Such methods should be guided by the development of competencies of a childlike specialist, the involvement of streamers in active cognitive and practical activities, the manifestation of initiative in the process of cognition. Passive assimilation of educational programs is excluded. The presence of modern infrastructure in the educational process. It should be based

on information, technological, organizational and communication components that help to apply new forms and methods of teaching, in particular distance education. Innovative technologies in education are used on the basis of the application of certain approaches to teaching, i.e. principles that include requirements and goals that are the basis for the development of new technologies. All innovations in the pedagogical sphere are based on the fact that society strictly corresponds to the current stage of socio-economic development. Currently, they should focus on the development of Students ' Independence, the formation of self - learning and self-development skills, the conscious assimilation of educational programs, and not mechanically.

Full information about the procedure for the organization of a special preschool educational institution, property and funds, the organization of the educational and educational and wellness process in a special preschool educational institution, the participants of the educational process and the management of a special preschool educational institution are indicated in the "regulation on a special state preschool educational institution". In particular, taking into account advanced foreign experience, urgent tasks were set to create conditions for the comprehensive intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development of children, improve the quality of preschool education, radically improve the quality preparation of children for school in preschool institutions, introduce modern educational programs and technologies widely used in world practice into the educational process, improve the mechanism of training and Especially since insufficient conditions were created for the activities of preschools, the buildings were neglected and lay empty, they were not used effectively, and strategic tasks in seven directions were outlined, which should be carried out in the first half of next year.

Almost all preschool educational organizations in our country are equipped with modern computer and telecommunication technologies. This, in turn, requires a new approach of educators to their labor activities. The introduction of new technologies into the educational process changes the role and role of the educator through a new approach, and not to the fact that he is squeezed by technical means, turning his educational activities again into a profession based on a lush, creative and creative approach.

In conclusion, in recent years, modern innovative IT technology has been widely used to occupy a dominant position for the organization of direct educational and methodological work in preschool education. Teachers, who have successfully mastered computer literacy, can open up a wide range of

opportunities for students, and this is not limited to presentations and demonstration of teaching rollers. In the context of a huge selection of locally developing programs, it is very difficult for fathers to choose what fully meets age, and educational needs are provided. Obtaining a competent opinion makes it possible to create optimal conditions for the functioning of this issue age Development children, creating the necessary things for the establishment of effective cooperation with family representatives of family representatives, increasing the prestige of the teacher in the eyes of parents.

References:

1. Рузиматов, Р. Я., Махкамов, Г. М., Отажонова, С. Р., & Турсунова, Ш. А. (2017). Промышленное развитие в Коканде, причины экологических проблем (1956-1975гг.). Высшая школа, (6), 77-78.
2. Isabayeva, M. M., & Otajonova, S. R. An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal.
3. Isabayeva, M. M., & Otajonova, S. R. (2021). Pedagogical factors of preparation of future teachers of biology for professional-pedagogical activities. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(6), 48-51.
4. Otajonova, S. (2021, July). PESTS OF FRUIT ORCHARDS IN THE TERRITORY OF KOKAND. In Конференции.
5. Otajonova, S. (2021). PESTS OF FRUIT ORCHARDS IN THE TERRITORY OF KOKAND: <https://doi.org/10.47100/conferences.v1i1.1318>. In RESEARCH SUPPORT CENTER CONFERENCES (No. 18.06).
6. Асқарова, М. А., Отажонова, С. Р., Алимова, М. Б., & Ирматова, М. Д. (2020). READING-INTELLIGENCE AS A CAPACITY-BUILDING TOOL. Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology, 2(7), 398-402.
7. Rakhimova, G., Narimonova, Z., Otajonova, S., & Abdulxaeva, M. (2019). Stereotypy and poetics of the endemic of recit. Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems, 11(7), 966-969.
8. Norquzieva, D. S., & Abdullaeva, N. R. (2019). PSYCHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF AGGRESSIVE BEHAVIOR IN ADOLESCENCE. Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology, 1(6), 490-495.
9. Khamidovna, M. I., Sheralievna, N. D., & Okhunovna, M. D. (2022). CONFLICT MANAGEMENT AND TYPES OF CONFLICTS AMONG MINORS. International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education, 14(7).
10. Sheralievna, N. D. (2022). FORMATION OF CONSTRUCTIVE BEHAVIOR AS A FACTOR IN THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SCHOOLCHILDREN'S EDUCATION. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 10(12), 1212-1216.

11. Sheralievna, N. D. (2021). DYNAMICS OF CONSTRUCTIVE BEHAVIOR FORMATION IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(10), 666-669.
12. Sheralievna, N. D. (2022). FORMATION OF CONSTRUCTIVE BEHAVIOR AS A FACTOR IN THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SCHOOLCHILDREN'S EDUCATION. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(12), 1212-1216.
13. Norqo'Ziyeva, D. S. (2021). ILK O'SPIRINLARNI KASBGA YO'NALTIRISHNING AYRIM PSIXOLOGIK MASALALARI. *Scientific progress*, 1(6), 1188-1192.
14. Бойтемирова, З., & Орипов, Э. (2016). РОЛЬ ДЕМОКРАТИЧЕСКИХ ИНСТИТУТОВ В ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИИ НАСЛЕДОВАНИЯ ТРАДИЦИОННЫХ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ. In *СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ К ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ КОНЦЕПЦИЙ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО РЕГУЛИРОВАНИЯ И УПРАВЛЕНИЯ В СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИХ СИСТЕМАХ* (pp. 30-32).
15. Boytemirova, Z. (2020). Youth and Spiritual Security. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(12), 181-183.
16. Aminova, M. M. (2021). The value of "5 initiatives" in the spiritual and moral education of students of secondary school. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(6), 38-42.
17. Mutalibovna, A. M. The Impact of Globalization on National Culture and Its Protection Problems. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(12), 210-212.
18. Mutalibovna, A. M. The Modern Importance of Studying the Scientific Heritage of Ibn Khaldun. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(12), 229-232.
19. Аминова, М. М. (2020). ЗНАЧЕНИЕ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ В ВОСПИТАНИИ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ МОЛОДЕЖИ. *Интернаука*, (22-2), 51-52.
20. Mutalibovna, A. M. INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO MODERN YOUTH EDUCATION.
21. Shamsiddinov, B. J., & Jakbaraliyva, Z. (2022). Scientific and Empirical Relations of Philosophy and Literature. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 7, 70-73.
22. Шамсиддинов, Б. Ж., & Жакбаралиева, З. О. (2022). АБУ АЛИ ИБН СИНО ТИББИЙ ТАРБИЯ ХУСУСИДА. *Oriental Art and Culture*, 3(2), 670-674.
23. Шамсиддинов, Б. Ж., & Алиев, А. А. Ў. (2022). ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА КЎППАРТИЯВИЙЛИК ТИЗИМИ ВА ХУСУСИЙ ТАДБИРКОРЛИК. *Oriental Art and Culture*, 3(2), 675-682.

24. Jakbrovich, S. B. (2021, July). THE RELATIONS OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP WITH SELF-GOVERNMENT INSTITUTIONS. In Euro-Asia Conferences (pp. 64-69).
25. Jakbarovich, S. B. (2021, July). DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP AS A SOCIO-ECONOMIC BASIS OF CIVIL SOCIETY. In Euro-Asia Conferences (pp. 69-72).
26. Шамсиддинов, Б. Ж. (2021). ЖАМИЯТ МАЪНАВИЙ ҲАЁТИДА ТАДБИРКОР ВА ИШБИЛАРМОНЛАР ИШТИРОКИНИНГ ЎРНИ ВА УНИНГ ИЖТИМОЙ-ФАЛСАФИЙ ТАЛҚИНИ. Oriental Art and Culture, 2(4), 565-574.
27. Шамсиддинов, Б. Ж. (2021). ХУСУСИЙ ТАДБИРКОР ВА ИШБИЛАРМОНЛАР ФАОЛИЯТИНИНГ ОИЛА ВА МАҲАЛЛА ФАРОВОНЛИГИГА ТАЪСИРИ. Oriental Art and Culture, 2(4), 452-456.
28. Бойкузиева, Г. (2020). ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ ЖЕНЩИН В СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПОЛИТИЧЕСКОЙ ЖИЗНИ ОБЩЕСТВА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. In ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКЕ (pp. 27-31).
29. Мирахмедов, Ж. М. (2017). Тарих фалсафий тадқиқот предмети сифатида. Молодой ученый, (4-2), 26-27.
30. Мирахмедов, Ж. М. (2017). Бағрикенглик ижтимоий-фалсафий қадрият. Молодой ученый, (4-2), 27-28.
31. Мирахмедов, Ж. М. (2016). Теоретическая подготовка студентов к социологическим исследованиям в практической и самостоятельной работе. In Молодежь и наука: реальность и будущее (pp. 318-319).
32. Мирахмедов, Ж. М. (2016). Некоторые аспекты проблемных концепций осмысления динамики научного знания. In Молодежь и наука: реальность и будущее (pp. 245-247).
33. МИРАХМЕДОВ, Ж. М., & БАБАЕВА, Н. М. (2016). К ВОПРОСУ О СУЩНОСТИ СОЦИОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ. In Будущее науки-2016 (pp. 16-19).
34. Muhsinovich, M. J. (2020). SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL INTERPRETATION OF THE CONCEPTS OF SPIRITUAL SAFETY AND HISTORICAL CONSCIOUSNESS. European science review, (9-10), 39-41.
35. Mirakhmedov, J. M. (2020). SOCIAL AND PHILOSOPHICAL INTERPRETATION OF THE CONCEPTS OF NATIONAL AND SPIRITUAL SECURITY. Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University, 2(8), 171-174.
36. Muhsinovich, M. J. (2020). FEATURES OF MANIFESTATION OF HISTORICAL CONSCIOUSNESS IN NATIONAL-SPIRITUAL SECURITY. Евразийский Союз Ученых, (4-9 (73)), 65-66.

37. Мирахмедов, Д. М. ФИЛОСОФСКИЙ ПОДХОД ПРИ ИЗУЧЕНИИ ИСТОРИЧЕСКОГО РАЗУМА.
38. Aminjonovna, S. O. (2021). The Importance of The Spiritual Heritage of Uzbek Enlighteners in the Education of Youth.
39. Орипов, Э. Ш., & Худойбергганов, Ш. Ш. (2020). ВИРТУАЛЬНЫЙ МИР: СОДЕРЖАНИЕ И СУЩНОСТЬ. In ВОПРОСЫ НАУКИ 2020: ПОТЕНЦИАЛ НАУКИ И СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ (pp. 53-60).
40. Худойбергганов, Ш. Ш., & Орипов, Э. Ш. (2020). ШОТЛАНД ОЛИМИ УИЛЬЯМ ЭРСКИН НИГОҲИДА БОБУР ТИМСОЛИ. In ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКЕ (pp. 187-190).
41. Oripov, E. S. (2021). HISTORICAL AND PHILOSOPHICAL ROOTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF TRADITIONAL VALUES. Journal of Central Asian Social Studies, 2(01), 122-127.
42. Орипов, Э. Ш., & Абдурахмонов, З. М. (2020). ФИЛОСОФСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ НОВОЙ СИСТЕМЫ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ. In ВОПРОСЫ НАУКИ 2020: ПОТЕНЦИАЛ НАУКИ И СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ (pp. 61-68).
43. Shavkatovich, O. E. (2022). MILLIY G'OYA VA AN'ANAVIY QADRIYATLARGA DIALEKTIV YONDOSHUV. Oriental Art and Culture, 3(1), 261-265.
44. Abdurahmonovich, A. H. (2021). THE ISSUE OF INTERPRETING THE WORLD (BEING) NATURE ON THE THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF NATIONAL EDUCATION OF THE UZBEK PEOPLE. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 2(07), 140-143.
45. Abdurahmonovich, A. H. (2022). A METHODOICAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL APPROACH TO INCREASE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHING 7TH GRADE EDUCATION IN A GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOL. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(12), 187-188.
46. Ортиқов, О. И. (2020). ИЖТИМОЙ-ФАЛСАФИЙ МЕРОСДА МИЛЛИЙЛИК МАСАЛАСИ. Интернаука, (10-3), 63-65.
47. Urinboyev, D. (2019). Thoughts About Stratagema Of Western And Eastern Thinkers. Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University, 1(4), 147-151.
48. Bakhtiyorovich, U. D. (2022). Features of the manifestation of strategems and the relationship between them. ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(11), 96-100.

